

Retrospective Review of Hernia Recurrence Rates following Mesh Verses Non-Mesh Repair Techniques

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Abstract:

Background: Hernia repair, a common surgery, can reduce recurrence and improve patient outcomes. Mesh repair is used for abdominal wall reinforcement; however, its merits and cons are debated.

Methods: This retrospective cohort analysis included 100 tertiary care hospital hernia repair patients from August 2023 to June 2024. Half the patients had mesh and half non-mesh repairs. The data set included postoperative issues, surgery details, and patient demographics. Chi-square testing and logistic regression were used to evaluate secondary outcomes and hernia recurrence rates between mesh repair and non-mesh repair groups.

Results: Mesh surgery reduced hernia recurrence by 6% compared to 20% following non-mesh repair ($p = 0.03$). The two groups had similar rates of chronic discomfort (10% vs. 16%, $p = 0.38$) and postoperative infection (4% vs. 6%, $p = 0.65$). In 2% of mesh repair cases, migration occurred. Although not statistically significant, the mesh repair group had a longer operation (75.3 ± 15.2 minutes vs. 70.6 ± 14.8 minutes, $p = 0.12$) and hospital stay (3.2 ± 1.1 days vs. 3.6 ± 1.3 days, $p = 0.09$).

Conclusion: Our study found that mesh surgery reduces hernia recurrence without worsening short-term issues. Given the results, mesh repair should be used for hernia procedures to improve patient outcomes. Future research should consider long-term consequences and procedure efficacy in different surgical settings and patient populations.

Keywords: Chronic pain, Hernia repair, Mesh, Recurrence rates, surgical outcomes.

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Introduction

Background on Hernia Repairs: A hernia occurs when an organ or fatty tissue protrudes through a muscle or connective tissue fissure. Inguinal, femoral, and umbilical hernias are prevalent [1]. Surgical surgery to straighten and strengthen the affected area is the main treatment. Mesh and non-mesh repairs were the dominant surgical techniques. Unlike non-mesh repair, which sutures the patient's tissue, mesh repair strengthens the incision with synthetic material. Mesh repair is becoming more popular since it may reduce recurrence. In cases of frail tissue or recurring hernias, mesh can support the weak area [2].

Mesh repair has many benefits, but it can cause infection, chronic pain, and mesh migration. Even though non-mesh repair is less popular, it's still an option for qualified individuals and has positives and cons [3].

Significance of the Study: Improved hernia surgery outcomes require awareness of mesh and non-mesh repair approaches' pros and cons. This study aims to compare hernia recurrence rates after these two surgeries. Recurrence rate analysis may reveal which strategy improves long-term outcomes, improving patient care and therapy decisions. Surgical advice and personalised hernia repair approaches may also benefit from the study.

Figure 1: Recurrent Hernia (Source: [4])

Objectives

- To compare hernia recurrence rates following mesh and non-mesh repair over time.
- To identify hernia recurrence risk factors by comparing mesh repair and non-mesh repair groups.
- To evaluate each repair method's hazards and clinical outcomes.

Hernia Repair Techniques: [5] Study have compared hernia repair treatments, which have all altered over time. The traditional procedure was tissue or non-mesh mending. Shouldice and Bassini suturing of fascia and muscles were done extensively. These approaches were associated with higher recurrence rates and longer healing times.

Synthetic mesh revolutionised hernia repairs. Late 20th-century research found that mesh repair reduced recurrence rates more than tissue healing. [6] Pioneered tension-free mesh repair for inguinal hernias. The Lichtenstein technique and laparoscopic mesh repair have consistently shown quicker recovery times and reduced recurrence rates [7]. Lightweight, absorbable, and non-absorbable meshes have been studied and each kind has pros and cons. Heavyweight meshes provide stronger reinforcement but can cause more pain and infection, while lightweight meshes produce less chronic pain but a higher recurrence rate.

Recurrence Rates in Mesh and Non-Mesh Repairs: Recurrence is a key sign of hernia repair success and mesh repairs reduce recurrence, according to various studies [8]. In a meta-analysis and systematic review by [9], mesh repairs had recurrence rates of 2-4% and non-mesh repairs 8-10%. This implies that mesh repair reduces recurrence and this applies to inguinal, femoral, and incisional hernias.

Laparoscopic mesh repair has considerably lower recurrence rates than open mesh surgery. A randomised controlled experiment by [10] indicated that open mesh repair had a 10.1% recurrence rate and laparoscopic mesh repair 4.9% over two years. Despite requiring specialised equipment, this technique often reduces postoperative pain and speeds up recovery [11]. Mesh migration, infection, and chronic pain are concerns. [12] suggests that these hazards may outweigh the benefits of lower recurrence rates in some patients. Despite increased recurrence rates, non-mesh repairs may assist patients with prior mesh infections or substantial comorbidities.

Mesh is recommended for hernia repairs, although there are still gaps in the study. Mesh types' long-term consequences have not been extensively investigated. Most studies have one- to five-year follow-ups. Long-term data is needed to understand mesh material lifespan and difficulties over decades. There are few high-quality, randomised controlled trials comparing mesh types in certain patient populations. Many current studies are observational or use small sample sizes, therefore the results may not apply to a larger population. Synthetic mesh is expensive in low-resource locations, and there is no data on its cost-effectiveness compared to non-mesh repairs.

Patients should have customised hernia repair treatments. Current guidelines support mesh repairs, although the optimum method for a patient depends on age, comorbidities, and surgery history. Future study on customised techniques that account for these disparities may improve results and reduce difficulties.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: From August 2023 to June 2024, researchers at a tertiary care centre looked back at a group of patients. The goal of this study was to find out which types of hernia repairs—mesh or non-mesh were more likely to happen again. The study followed the rules of the Declaration of Helsinki, and the study protocol was approved by the institution's ethics council.

Sample Size and Selection Criteria: One hundred individuals who had hernia repairs done throughout the study period made up the sample size.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults 18 or older who have primary hernia repair surgery.
- Doctor-confirmed inguinal, femoral, umbilical, or incisional hernia patients.
- Who received mesh or non-mesh treatment for injuries.
- Complete retrospective access to patient data before, during, and after operation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Those with recurring hernias after surgery.
- Those with complicated hernias such as strangulated or incarcerated.
- Comorbidities including severe cardiovascular disease or uncontrolled diabetes can affect surgical outcomes.
- Emergency hernia repair patients.
- According to surgical approach, patients were divided into mesh repair and non-mesh repair groups. To compare fairly, each group had 50 patients.

Data Collection Methods: Hospital electronic medical records were queried for data. Patient demographics (age, sex, BMI), comorbidities

(diabetes, hypertension, COPD), hernia type and location, surgical repair method (mesh vs. non-mesh), surgical technique (open vs. laparoscopic), surgery length, and intraoperative complications were considered relevant.

Postoperative follow-up included data on hernia recurrence, postoperative complications (infection, prolonged pain, mesh migration), and patient outcomes. A hernia that was clinically diagnosed and confirmed by imaging or physical examination at the same location was a recurrence. For recurrence assessment, the standard follow-up was one year after surgery. Analysis of extracted data was done in a password-protected database.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS 25 was used for statistical analysis. To summarise patient demographics and baseline characteristics, descriptive statistics were used. Means and standard deviations represented continuous values, whereas frequencies and percentages represented categorical variables. The mesh and non-mesh repair groups were compared on hernia recurrence rate using the chi-square test for categorical data.

Logistic regression analysis identified age, sex, BMI, comorbidities, and surgical repair as hernia recurrence risk variables. Secondary outcomes like surgical complications and patient outcomes could be analysed using appropriate statistical techniques. A p-value below 0.05 was statistically significant.

Kaplan-Meier survival graphs showed the difference in time to hernia recurrence between the two groups, and sensitivity studies tested robustness. For accuracy and validity, a biostatistician reviewed all analyses.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Sample

Demographic Variable	Mesh Repair (n=50)	Non-Mesh Repair (n=50)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	55.2 ± 10.4	54.8 ± 9.8	0.82
Gender (Male)	35:15	33:17	0.70
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	26.3 ± 3.5	25.8 ± 3.7	0.52
Diabetes (%)	18 (36%)	20 (40%)	0.69
Hypertension (%)	22 (44%)	21 (42%)	0.85
COPD (%)	10 (20%)	8 (16%)	0.61

In the study, patients in the mesh repair group had an average age of 55.2 years (± 10.4), while those in the non-mesh repair group had an average age of 54.8 years (± 9.8). The two groups were not significantly different with a p-value of 0.82. Men and women were equally represented in the mesh (35:15) and non-mesh (33:17) groups (p=0.70). Mesh group had an average BMI of 26.3 kg/m² (±

3.5), while non-mesh group had 25.8 kg/m² (± 3.7) (p=0.52). The two groups had similar rates of comorbidities such diabetes (36% vs. 40%, p=0.69), hypertension (44% vs. 42%, p=0.85), and COPD (20% vs. 16%, p=0.61).

These data demonstrate that the two groups were initially very similar.

Table 2: Recurrence Rates in Mesh vs. Non-Mesh Repairs

Outcome	Mesh Repair (n=50)	Non-Mesh Repair (n=50)	p-value
Recurrence Rate (%)	3 (6%)	10 (20%)	0.03

In our study, mesh repair patients had a 6% recurrence rate compared to 20% ($p = 0.03$).

This shows how mesh techniques can reduce hernia recurrence following surgery. Mesh hernia repairs may provide better long-term results because to its

structural support and lower recurrence rate. This supports mesh repair's status as the gold standard in hernia surgery, as it reduces recurrence and improves outcomes.

Statistical Significance of the Findings

Table 3: Statistical Significance of the Findings

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Mesh Repair (vs. Non-Mesh)	0.25	0.07 - 0.86	0.03
Age	1.02	0.97 - 1.06	0.42
Gender (Male)	1.10	0.45 - 2.71	0.83
BMI	1.05	0.95 - 1.16	0.33
Diabetes	1.15	0.44 - 2.96	0.77
Hypertension	0.89	0.37 - 2.12	0.79
COPD	0.71	0.23 - 2.18	0.55

Recurrence rates of hernias repaired with mesh are substantially lower than those fixed without mesh, with an OR of 0.25 (95% CI: 0.07 - 0.86, $p = 0.03$).

Patients who received mesh surgery had a 75% decreased chance of hernia recurrence. Age, BMI,

and comorbidities (diabetes, hypertension, COPD) are critical determinants in patient care, but they did not independently predict hernia recurrence in our study population.

Secondary Outcomes

Table 4: Secondary Outcomes

Outcome	Mesh Repair (n=50)	Non-Mesh Repair (n=50)	p-value
Postoperative Infection (%)	2 (4%)	3 (6%)	0.65
Chronic Pain (%)	5 (10%)	8 (16%)	0.38
Mesh Migration (%)	1 (2%)	-	-
Mean Duration of Surgery (minutes)	75.3 ± 15.2	70.6 ± 14.8	0.12
Mean Hospital Stay (days)	3.2 ± 1.1	3.6 ± 1.3	0.09

Mesh repair significantly reduces hernia recurrence rates (6% vs. 20%, $p = 0.03$), confirming its long-term efficacy. Since postoperative infections were low and comparable (4% vs. 6%, $p = 0.65$), both groups followed similar infection control methods despite employing distinct procedures.

Mesh repair reduced chronic discomfort by 10% ($p = 0.38$), but the difference was not statistically significant. In the repaired mesh group, just 2% migrated. Even though there was no statistically significant difference, mesh repair patients had longer surgeries and hospital stays. These findings support the hypothesis that mesh surgery can reduce hernia recurrence without increasing morbidity.

Discussion

This study compares mesh and non-mesh hernia repair procedures. Our data showed that mesh surgery reduced hernia recurrence (6% vs. 20%, $p = 0.03$). This confirms mesh's long-term reduction

in hernia recurrence by supporting the weakened abdominal wall.

Secondary outcomes like surgical infection and chronic pain favoured mesh repair, but not statistically.

Low and similar postoperative infection rates in mesh and non-mesh groups (4% vs. 6%, $p = 0.65$), showing both surgical approaches reduced infection. Chronic pain rates were reduced in the mesh repair group (10% vs. 16%, $p = 0.38$), but not statistically significant.

This may be due to the short sample size or patient discomfort. Good surgical technique and mesh selection likely minimised mesh migration (2% in our study group), a mesh repair concern. Clinical decision-makers should consider the mesh repair group's longer surgery and hospital stay when comparing the merits and downsides of greater procedural time and resource use versus lower recurrence. Both differences were not statistically significant ($p = 0.12$ and 0.09 , respectively).

Table 5: Comparison Table

Study Title	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Retrospective Cohort Study	100 (50 mesh, 50 non-mesh)	Mesh repair significantly reduces hernia recurrence (6% vs. 20%, $p = 0.03$). Comparable rates of postoperative infection and chronic pain.	Single-center design, short-term follow-up (1 year), potential for selection bias in retrospective data collection.
Study 1 [13]	Prospective Comparative Study	500	Introduction of tension-free mesh repair. Lower recurrence rates with mesh compared to tissue repair.	Single-arm design, variations in surgical techniques and follow-up protocols across centers.
Study 2 [14]	Meta-analysis	300	Mesh repair associated with significantly lower recurrence rates across multiple hernia types (2-4% vs. 8-10%).	Heterogeneity across included studies, potential publication bias, variable quality of evidence.
Study 3 [15]	Randomized Controlled Trial	1000 (500 mesh, 500 non-mesh)	Lower recurrence rates with laparoscopic mesh repair compared to open mesh repair (4.9% vs. 10.1%).	Large sample size, multicenter design, long-term outcomes assessed. Potential for variability in surgical technique.

In this retrospective cohort research, mesh surgery reduced hernia recurrence rates by 6% (vs. 20%, $p = 0.03$). This finding supports prior evidence that mesh can improve surgery results by providing long-term abdominal wall support. The study found equal postoperative infection and discomfort rates in mesh and non-mesh groups. This shows that mesh reduces recurrence but does not significantly boost short-term effects. Several constraints must be considered. The study's single-center design may limit its applicability to various patient demographics and surgeries. The one-year follow-up period may not capture mesh repair's long-term effects, such as persistent pain or infections. Retrospective data collection cannot eliminate selection bias despite extensive data validation. Thus, results should be interpreted cautiously. Hernia recurrence rates are reduced by tension-free mesh repair in prospective trials like Study 1 and meta-analyses like Study 2. Randomised controlled trials, like Study 3, compare surgical techniques over longer follow-up periods and with bigger sample sizes, providing robust evidence. Future research that addresses these limits may enhance clinical advice and hernia repair surgery outcomes.

Strengths: The thorough method and rich data from a reputed tertiary care centre make this study strong. Due to the retrospective methodology, a large sample size ($n=100$) was included throughout a defined research period, increasing statistical power and making the findings more relevant to similar patient populations. The systematic follow-up and inclusion of primary and recurrent hernias ensured consistent outcomes. Surgical outcomes, postoperative complications, and recurrence rates have been studied. This holistic method provides a deeper understanding of repair treatments'

therapeutic effects to enable doctors make patient-specific decisions.

Limitations: Despite its strengths, this study has serious drawbacks. Data collection in a retrospective study has limits and biases. For instance, medical records may be incomplete. Retrospective studies may include selection bias and unaccounted-for confounding factors despite comprehensive data validation and anonymization. The study's single-center methodology may have biased patient selection and surgical methods, making the results unapplicable to other demographics or circumstances. Due to healthcare infrastructure, patient management, and surgical procedures, the results may not apply to different populations. With mesh-associated concerns including chronic discomfort or infections, the one-year follow-up may not capture long-term results or complications connected to hernia repair procedures. Despite our statistical analysis to control for confounders, the study's sample size may have prevented us from identifying smaller differences in findings between the mesh and non-mesh repair groups.

Conclusion

Mesh repair reduces hernia recurrence rates by 6% vs. 20% ($p = 0.03$) in our cohort analysis. Mesh strengthens the abdominal wall permanently, making it effective in hernia repair surgery. Since both mesh and non-mesh groups had similar rates of postoperative infection and persistent pain, mesh reduces the risk of recurrence but not short-term complications. These findings have major therapeutic treatment implications. For surgeons seeking to limit recurrence, mesh repair is a better hernia surgery option. Given the comparable infection and chronic discomfort safety profile of

mesh, there is no reason to worry about acute complications after surgery. Clinicians should consider patient-specific characteristics and weigh the merits and cons of mesh repair, including procedural problems and longer operation times.

Recommendations for Future Research

Several crucial topics should influence future research. Longitudinal studies that follow patients for more than a year are needed to determine the long-term implications of mesh repair, such as chronic discomfort and infections. A multicenter study may also apply results to more patient groups and surgical techniques. Standardising surgery and follow-up practices may reduce variability and improve trial comparability. Depending on hernia size, location, and demographics, meshes types and surgical approaches can improve outcomes. To understand this, comparative effectiveness studies should examine these variances. Future study can fill these gaps with stronger data to support evidence-based clinical standards and improve hernia repair surgical results. Incorporating extensive study results into clinical practice will improve hernia repair care and decision-making worldwide.

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